

E -Patient Deidentified Record Integration using Cloud Computing

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Abstract: With the development of science and technology, the design of modern architecture is becoming more and more attractive. Now a days the medical fields become more wide development in machinery the same way the data storage also developed higher . The main reason for proposing the paper is to store the patient data into the cloud. The patient can access the data from anywhere at any time. . The delivering of public health solutions can lead to increased efficiency in health related data. Many nations across the globe have launched aggressive stimulus programs aimed at solving public health care problems in efficient way .This paper proposed for maintain the patient health record in cloud computing.

Keywords:Cloud computing ,Mobile Application, Server, Website, Mobile Phone, Patients, Doctors, Hospitals

I. INTRODUCTION

Cloud computing takes the emphasis away from local computers. It is less about the machine in use at home or on the move and more about what happening on computers many miles away. Instead of storing the information on PC, smart phone or tablet, data can be kept remotely. It will then be made available to any device that is capable of reading it. The benefit of this is very clear: no one needs to be tied to a computer or phone; all that is needed is a way of accessing the data and that can be done from any machine.

The essential characteristics of cloud computing are :

A. On-demand self-service: a consumer can provision computing capabilities, such as server time and network storage, as needed.

B. Broad network access: broad range of network accessibilities by various client platforms.

C. Resource pooling: the provider's computing capabilities are pooled to serve multiple consumers using a multi-tenant model. Resources are dynamically assigned and reassigned according to consumer demand.

D. Rapid elasticity: capabilities can be rapid, elastically provisioned, and in some cases automatic; the consumer capabilities available for provisioning often appear to be unlimited and can be purchased in any quantity at any time.

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Introduction to Project:

Nowadays the Patient details has stored in manual way so the data has been gets destroyed due to the some natural disaster and some natural calamities. If the hospitals has got fire the data in the hospitals has been damaged so the patient entire details has been damaged. So the next time patient got treatment the wrong treatment has been done. This paper proposed that the patient details to be stored in Cloud Computing They can access the data any where from any time if they needed. So the patient gets correct treatment instead of wrong treatment. If the patient Goes to hospital for any checkup their details will be updated to the server portal which has been allocated for the patient. The token system also has been implement in this project the patient can book their token from their home in their mobile application, So the waiting time for the patient is reduced. The patient can book the token when they need to go for hospital this can be done with the mobile application.

II. METHODOLOGY:

1. This paper propose the Patient details to be stored to the Cloud storage which the user can easily access their data.
2. The Patient details has been collected. and converted into the soft copy(X-Ray) and uploaded to their portal.

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3.The patient has separate mobile application to view the details of their description(medical report) and treatment methods.

4.The hospital has separate website for uploading the details and viewing the tokens.

Design of the System:

The main component of this system is Cloud computing. The Hospital should registered. The patient details will uploaded in cloud. The patient want to view the details of their report and the mobile application and Web application for uploading and viewing the details

Importance and Motivation:

The benefit of this is very clear, no one needs to be tied to a computer or phone. Like laptops, smart phones, tablets, or any other device capable of accessing data.

- To reduce the paperwork of the hospital and patients.
- To reduce time spent over transportation.
- To reduce inter dependency of hospitals over patients and viceversa.
- To introduce fast and efficient information sharing and response remedy
- To increase dependency on technology to help the people at their needed time.

Hardware & Software Requirements:

A. Laptop:

It is used for installation of different software which is required for generate cloud and various assisting application. Laptop will act like server and data cloud storage. laptop has been used in hospital side for uploading the patient details into the cloud computing. The website has

been used for uploading the patient details and viewing the tokens booked by patients.

B. Mobile Phone:

The mobile phone has been used for applying the token and viewing the details of their treatment procedures and the medical prescription

C. JAVA Script:

The java scripit was used for developing an Website for uploading the patient details and maintain the patient details and viewing the token system.

D. PHP Server:

The PHP server has been used to maintain the website the and to maintain the documents of patient and retrieved the patient details when every they needed to view t details.

Work Flow:

Web page development and cloud storage is done. The snapshots of few web pages and mobile application for this project are as below:

1. The login page for the web page in Hospital side this login has been used for login the page for uploading the patient details and viewing the tokens

2. Dashboard page: The dashboard page of web page has been used for creating the tokens and uploading the number of active patients and uploading the details

3. Patient List: The total number of patient details has been displayed in this navigation menu

P-ID	NAME	PHONE	ADDRESS	GENDER	ACTION
1	Narendiran	767863247	vellore	M	EDIT ACTIVE
2	Vidhya Narendiran	767863247	Chennai	F	EDIT ACTIVE
4	Siva Kumar M	9788333048	Walajpet	M	EDIT ACTIVE
5	Arun Kumar	9876543210	Chennai	M	EDIT ACTIVE
6	Jayachitra Balu	9449496890	vellore	F	EDIT ACTIVE
7	Manisha pre Saja	9445000393	walaja	F	EDIT ACTIVE
8	Ela Maren ragav	9876543092	vclmottur	M	EDIT ACTIVE
9	kabliian	767863247	V.C.Mottur	M	EDIT ACTIVE

6. Viewing Details: The patient can view their details and see their medical prescription the way of medical treatment and their X-Ray.

ACTIVE ALL TOKENS RUNNING

#2 Vidhya Narendiran
23yrs | F | 173 Cms
Diabetes

Today		Last - Report	
Date	23/01/2020	Date	09/01/2020
BP	-	BP	-
Before Fasting	-	Before Fasting	-
After Fasting	-	After Fasting	-
Weight	-	Weight	Kgs
Complaint	Fever Tsttrt	Complaint	Stomach Pain

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4. Mobile login page: The Mobile application has been used for viewing the details and applying the tokens

5. Mobile Dashboard: The mobile dashboard contains total number of patient came for hospital and total token for today.

III. FUTURE SCOPE

In the upcoming generation the medical is one of the basic need so this fast world the medical field should be developed by not in only machinery and equipment the documents and files to be in soft copy and patient need to be viewed in their mobile phones instead of going to hospital for appointment. In emergency cases like accident of patient their medical details has been taken from mobile instead of waiting to know about the patient.

IV. CONCLUSION

The patient information stored in cloud server is useful for future verification and aware of health of patients and treatment is avail for their state of health. This will help the patient to travel for long distance because they can view their report in online. This project is implemented for betterment of people health to make easier form anywhere at any time.

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